

Storage Research Infrastructure Eco-System

D2.1 – “Validation of the Selection Panel”

WP 2 – Transnational and Virtual Access to World-class Research Infrastructures

Task 2.1 - Transnational access management

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DISSEMINATION LEVEL

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

ES	Energy Storage
SP	Selection Panel
TNA	Transnational Access
WP	Work Package

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1 TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS IN STORIES - INTRODUCTION

The aim of StoRIES is to provide researchers from Europe and beyond access to the world-class research infrastructures (RI) brought together in the StoRIES community.

Work Package 2 (WP2) is completely dedicated to this target. Task 2.1 of WP 2 focuses on the management of StoRIES transnational access (TNA), provides the rules and methodology (will be included in deliverables D2.2 and D2.3), and monitors the process. It also supports the preparation of the calls for proposals, collects the proposals from users and actively contributes to the various panels, such as Working Groups 2 and 3 of Work Package 1 (WP1) and the Selection Panel, which provide scientific expertise to the process.

The calls preparation rules will be described in deliverable D2.2 (WP2) and in deliverable D1.1 (WP1 – Definition of governance for the WGs) and submitted in M6. The TNA governance will be provided in deliverable D2.3. The governance of the Selection Panel is outlined in D6.1 Project Management Plan (WP6).

2 SELECTION PANEL ROLE IN THE TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS

The evaluation of the users proposals submitted in response to the StoRIES Transnational Access calls is performed in two steps:

- Pre-screening by Working Group 2 (WP1). Proposals that cannot be implemented under StoRIES TNA are sorted out after exchange with RI providers.
- Final evaluation of the pre-screened proposals by the Selection Panel.

To enable the best possible analysis of proposals and a forward-looking and fair selection of applications, the StoRIES Governing Board established officially the Selection Panel (SP) on 25 November 2021 during the StoRIES kick-off meeting.

The initial group of SP members is presented in the table below. Most of the members of the SP were identified during the StoRIES project application phase. Two were added after the project was approved and received funding. The members of the SP bring expertise from a wide range of energy storage technologies and related fields. They come from academia, research organisations as well as industry, and about 80% are not otherwise involved in StoRIES project.

The StoRIES Governing Board has decided to allow changes in the composition of the SP to ensure best practice in the evaluation process. Additional experts may join the SP throughout the life of the project, but they must be accepted by the Governing Board and provide a Letter of Support to StoRIES. The changes in the membership of SP will be published on the StoRIES website.

For each call for TNA applications, a group of 5-6 impartial experts (not from the host or home organisation of the TNA application, and with knowledge in the thematic area of the call) from SP will be identified to evaluate the applications. This will allow the best possible and fair evaluation of the TNA proposals.

Table 1: StoRIES Selection Panel membership approved on 25th November 2021

Name	Organisation	ES technology
Aelbrecht, Denis	EDF (FR)	Energy supplier
Akgül, Çağla Meral	Middle East Technical University (TR)	Thermal ES
Ausfelder, Florian	DECHEMA e.V. (DE)	Chemical ES
Avellan, Francois	EPFL (CH)	Mechanical ES
Balducci, Andrea	Friedrich-Schiller University (DE)	Electrochemical ES
Barelli, Linda	University of Perugia (IT)	Chemical ES
Barrio, Laura	University of Basque Country (ES)	Chemical ES
Blackman, Corey	SaltX	Chemical ES
Bodo, Enrico	University of Rome (IT)	Electrochemical ES
Bodoardo, Silvia	Politecnico di Torino (IT)	Electrochemical ES
Chaivazzo, Eliodoro	Politecnico di Torino (IT)	Thermal ES
Chazarra, Manuel	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (ES)	Mechanical ES
Copley, Mark	WMG University of Warwick (UK)	Electrochemical ES
Di Noto, Vito	University of Padova (IT)	Chemical ES
Ding, Yulong	University Birmingham (UK)	Mechanical ES, Thermal ES
Erden Topal, Yelda	Middle East Technical University (TR)	Thermal ES

Figgemeier, Egbert	RWTH Aachen (DE)	Electrochemical ES
Goede, Adelbert	DIFFER (NL)	Chemical ES
Iturbe, Rafael	ANTEC	Superconducting Magnetic ES
Kato, Yukitaka	Tokyo Institute of Technology (JP)	Thermal ES
Kruger, Klaus	Voith (DE)	Seawater Pumped ES
McTigue, Joshua	NREL (USA)	Pumped Thermal ES
Millingen, Magnus	Texel	Thermochemical ES
Morandi, Antonio	University of Bologna (IT)	Superconducting Magnetic ES
Navarra, Maria Assunta	Sapienza University of Rome (IT)	Electrochemical ES
Nonnemacher, Lukas	Uniper SE (DE)	Power Grids
Paillard, Elie	Polytechnic of Milan (IT)	Electrochemical ES
Persoglia, Sergio	ENeRG (IT)	Underground ES
Pollet, Bruno G.	NTNU Team Hydrogen Leader (NO)	Chemical ES
Ristić, Alenka	National Institute of Chemistry (SI)	Thermal ES
Schnuerch, Michael	Technische Universität Wien (AT)	Thermal ES
Weinberger, Peter	Technische Universität Wien (AT)	Thermal ES